

1 **A new non-parametric method for analyzing replicated point patterns in ecology**

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9

10 **Abstract**

11 Most ecological studies that involve point pattern analyses are based on a single plot, which
12 prevent the separation of the effects of various processes that could act simultaneously, as
13 well as limiting the conclusions that can be extracted from these studies. However,
14 considering the spatial distribution of individuals in several plots as replicates of the same
15 process could help to differentiate its specific effects from those of other confounding
16 processes. Thus, we introduce a new method for analyzing spatial point patterns that are
17 replicated according to a two-factorial design. By summarizing the spatial patterns as K -
18 functions, the proposed method computes the average K -functions for each level of the two
19 factors (i.e., predictors) and for each combination of levels, before estimating the sum of
20 squared deviations from the overall mean K -function. Inferences of the strength of the
21 relationship between the predictors, their interaction, and the spatial structure are made
22 based on a non-parametric bootstrap procedure, which considers the dependency among

23 spatial scales. We illustrate the proposed approach based on an analysis of the effects of
24 altitude (with two levels: low and high) and slope (with two levels: flat and steep slopes) on
25 the spatial pattern of *Croton wagneri*, a dominant shrub in an Andean dry scrubland. Our
26 method detected a significant effect of the interaction between slope and altitude, which
27 could not have been detected using current point pattern analysis methodology. The
28 prevalence of single-plot analysis in ecological studies may be due to a lack of familiarity
29 with appropriate methods for replicated point patterns, as well as the greater complexity of
30 these methods and the absence of appropriate software. Our approach can be applied to a
31 significant number of ecological questions while maintaining a simple, understandable, and
32 easily reportable methodological framework.

33

34 **Abbreviations.** ANOVA: analysis of variance, BTSS: between treatments sum of squares,
35 PCP: Poisson cluster process.

36 **Keywords:** *K*-function, second-order spatial structure, spatial modeling.

37

38 **Introduction**

39 The spatial ecology paradigm (Tilman and Kareiva 1998) highlights the relevance of space
40 for the functioning of ecosystems as well as recognizing that the assembly and functioning
41 of plant populations and communities are also governed by spatial processes. Following the
42 pioneering work of Watt (1947), extensive evidence has accumulated to demonstrate that
43 the spatial distribution of plant species is not random, but instead individuals often exhibit
44 local aggregation and/or over-dispersion within populations and communities (e.g., Watt

45 1947, Pielou 1977, Kenkel 1988, Barot et al. 1999, Condit et al. 2000). In this context,
46 point pattern analysis has emerged as a powerful tool for integrating space into ecological
47 theory, but more specifically for connecting the actual patterns with the processes that
48 generate them (Wiegand and Moloney 2014). A basic assumption when analyzing
49 ecological point patterns is that the patterns conserve some signature from past processes,
50 and thus they constitute an “ecological archive,” which can be used to recover information
51 regarding the underlying processes (McIntire and Fajardo 2009; Wiegand and Moloney
52 2014). For example, aggregated spatial patterns can be related to limited dispersal (e.g.,
53 Seidler and Plotkin 2006) and over-dispersed patterns to intraspecific competition (Kenkel
54 1988).

55 The links between processes and actual patterns are not always evident or direct because
56 they may be confounded by the interactions among several processes (Wiegand et al.
57 2009), or by the intrinsic spatial nature of the processes that generate the patterns (e.g.,
58 environmental heterogeneity; Getzin et al. 2008, Chacón-Labela et al. 2014, Jara-Guerrero
59 et al. 2015). Indeed, a methodological limitation that contributes to the prevalence of these
60 confounding effects is the fact that most ecological studies involving point pattern analysis
61 are based on only one plot (or on several plots that are analyzed individually). However, the
62 spatial distribution of plants in several plots can be considered as replicates of the same
63 process (Bagchi and Illian 2015), which could help to separate its effects from those of
64 other confounding processes (e.g., the typical confounding between a clustering process
65 and environmental heterogeneity; Law et al. 2009, Diggle 2014). As a consequence, the use
66 of replicated patterns combined with an appropriate sampling design would help to
67 generalize the insights gained from point pattern analysis, where this approach could also

68 be employed to test specific hypotheses related to specific processes that affect the spatial
69 structure of study populations or communities. For example, tests could determine whether
70 there are differences in aggregation between various groups of species in a community or
71 between life stages (i.e., adult vs. juvenile) in a population (LeMay et al. 2009), or if these
72 differences occur because the populations grow on different soil substrates (Schenk et al.
73 2003).

74 Methods for analyzing replicated point patterns are available in the statistical literature, but
75 they have been used only rarely in ecological studies (but see Schenk et al. 2003, LeMay et
76 al. 2009). Briefly, they can be classified into parametric and non-parametric methods
77 (Landau and Everall 2008). Parametric methods use maximum likelihood or pseudo-
78 likelihood methods to fit the parameters of a point process model. These methods have
79 been employed to fit certain homogeneous point processes such as pairwise interactions
80 (Diggle et al. 2000, Mateu 2001) or Gibbs point processes (Bell and Grunwald 2004). Non-
81 parametric methods evaluate differences in summary functions (mainly Ripley's K -
82 function) among experimental or observational groups. Two main alternative approaches
83 have been developed within the non-parametric methods: the method described by Diggle
84 et al. (1991), which is analogous to the analysis of variance (ANOVA) for a one-way
85 design, and the method proposed by Landau and Everall (2008) for repeated measures (and
86 other more complicated) designs [although the use of hierarchical Gaussian process
87 regression was reported by Myllymäki et al. (2014)]. In general, it is considered that the
88 performance of non-parametric methods is more efficient compared with parametric
89 methods and that they are less prone to model mis-specifications (Diggle et al. 2000,
90 Bagchi and Illian 2015). This versatility supports their use and application in ecological

91 contexts. In order to promote their use in ecological studies, Bagchi and Illian (2015)
92 recently summarized the non-parametric methods, where they focused mainly on the
93 repeated measures approach, which involves linear mixed modeling of parameters that
94 describe the differences in spatial aggregation among groups of treatments or the effects of
95 covariates, while considering random effects. This approach is extremely useful in some
96 contexts (e.g., when there are many groups or levels (and replicates) for each treatment),
97 but many important ecological questions can be answered more easily with even simpler
98 methods (Murtaugh 2007). In fact, compared with linear mixed models, non-parametric
99 ANOVA-like methods are less prone to errors and they are straightforward to explain and
100 understand (Murtaugh 2007).

101 In this study, we propose an extension of the method described by Diggle et al. (1991) for
102 replicated point patterns in the two-way case, where we focus on the interactions between
103 two factors that are considered in the (experimental) sampling design.

104 We applied this new method to a case study based on dry scrubland dominated by *Croton*
105 in Southern Ecuador. *Croton wagneri* Müll. Arg. is an endemic shrub, which comprises
106 most of the biomass in the Ecuadorian Dry Mountain Scrub ecosystem, where it acts as a
107 key ecosystem engineer by providing refuge and shelter from harsh environmental
108 conditions for many other species (Valencia et al. 2000, Espinosa et al. 2014); therefore, its
109 spatial structure governs the functioning of these communities. Observational evidence
110 demonstrates that *C. wagneri* populations have an aggregated spatial distribution and the
111 intensity of the spatial aggregation varies along an altitude gradient in response to changing
112 environmental conditions.

113 Similar to any other desert or semiarid shrub, the aggregated patterns of *C. wagneri* could
114 be the result of limited dispersal (Ellner and Shmida 1981, Seidler and Plotkin 2006),
115 facilitation (i.e., the nurse effect, Flores and Jurado 2003), a preference for favorable
116 microsites where water and nutrients are more accessible (Schlesinger et al. 1996, Rietkerk
117 et al. 2002), or a combination of all these mechanisms. In fact, it has been suggested that
118 the characteristic biphasic bare-cover mosaic in dryland areas is due to the interplay
119 between local positive interactions and competition for water, which generates scale-
120 dependent feedback, where this effect is locally positive but negative farther away
121 (Rietkerk and Van de Koppel 2008, Maestre and Escudero 2009). Both theoretical (Lefever
122 et al. 2009, Siteur et al. 2014) and empirical (Deblauwe et al. 2011) studies have shown that
123 different environmental conditions, particularly aridity and slopes (Lefever et al. 2009,
124 Deblauwe et al. 2011), can alter or modify this feedback, thereby yielding different spatial
125 configurations of standing biomass (Maestre and Escudero 2009).

126 In our case study, we aimed to test whether these mechanisms govern the spatial
127 distribution of *C. wagneri* individuals in a scrubland area that extends along an altitudinal
128 gradient (from 1000 to 2500 m), where the aridity decreases from lower to higher altitudes
129 (Richter and Moreira-Muñoz 2005). We hypothesized that the effect of aridity on the
130 spatial structure of *C. wagneri* would be modified by the slope. We expected that
131 populations on steeper slopes would be aggregated in a similar manner irrespective of
132 altitude (i.e., rainfall) because of the stressful conditions (thin soils and rapid run-off) that
133 prevail on steep slopes. By contrast, we expected that populations on gentle slopes or flat
134 ground would exhibit a marked effect of aridity, i.e., altitude, on aggregation. Translated
135 into the terminology of two-way ANOVA, we predict the existence of an interaction

136 between slope and altitude. We applied our extension of the method proposed by Diggle et
137 al. (1991) to the two-way design to test for the existence of this interaction. We compared
138 the results of our test with those obtained using a more traditional approach (e.g., Seidler
139 and Plotkin 2006), where we applied classical ANOVA to the parameters of a spatial point
140 process model (a Poisson cluster model) fitted to each *C. wagneri* pattern.

141 **Methods**

142 *Study site*

143 The study was conducted in southern Ecuador, on the slopes of an Andean valley (Alamala,
144 cantón Catamayo, 03°58'29''S, 01°25'22''W), which covered an altitudinal gradient from
145 1400 to 1900 m.a.s.l. The annual average temperature and rainfall range from 33.8°C and
146 423 mm respectively in the lower zone to 27.4°C and 562 mm in the upper zone. Rain is
147 mostly distributed from January to April but almost absent for the rest of the year (Espinosa
148 et al. 2014). Vegetation forms conspicuous perennial patches, which are interspersed with
149 bare soil areas (occupied by annual plants during the rainy season). *Croton wagneri*
150 (Eupobiaceae) is the dominant shrub that defines the vegetation patches, whereas other
151 perennial species are represented by isolated individuals (Espinosa et al. 2014).

152 *Data collection*

153 In total, 16 plots (with dimensions of ca 30 × 30 m) were studied at two altitude levels:
154 “low altitude” (between 1400 and 1500 m.a.s.l.) and “high altitude” (between 1750 and
155 1900 m.a.s.l.). At each altitudinal level, four plots were located on flat ground and four on
156 steep slopes (> 27° inclination). The plots at each altitude were located ≥200 m from each

157 other. In each plot, all of the *Croton wagneri* individuals were mapped using a compact
158 Electronic Laser Hypsometer TruPulse 360°, which allowed us to calculate the horizontal
159 distance, inclination, and azimuth (central angle) from a fixed common vertex to the
160 rooting point of each individual with a precision of 1 cm. Selected maps of *C. wagneri* for
161 each combination of slope and altitude are presented in Fig. 2. Maps of the spatial
162 distribution of *C. wagneri* in the 16 plots are provided in Figure S1 in the Appendix.

163 *Spatial pattern description*

164 To summarize the spatial pattern of *C. wagneri* in each plot, we used Ripley's K -function
165 (Ripley 1977). $\lambda K(r)$, where λ is the intensity of the plot, is the expected number of points
166 within in a circular area with radius r around a typical point in the pattern. The expected
167 value for a random pattern is $K(r) = \pi r^2$.

168 The K -functions were calculated using a standard unbiased estimator (Ripley 1976) with
169 isotropic edge correction as follows:

$$170 \hat{K}(r) = n^{-2} A \sum_{i=1}^n \sum_{j \neq i} w_{ij}^{-1} I(d_{ij} < r), \quad (1)$$

171 where d_{ij} represents the Euclidean distance between individuals i and j , $I(\cdot)$ is the indicator
172 function, and w_{ij}^{-1} is an edge correction, which is defined as the proportion of the
173 circumference of a circle centered on individual i with radius r contained within the
174 sampling area A .

175 To characterize the magnitude of aggregation in each plot, we also fitted a Poisson cluster
176 process (PCP) model to each observed K function using the minimum contrast method
177 (Diggle 2003). A PCP describes the formation of a pattern as a two-step process. First, a

178 Poisson pattern of “parent” points is generated with intensity ρ . Next, each parent point
 179 produces “offspring,” where the number of offspring per parent follows a Poisson
 180 distribution, and their locations are independent and isotropically normally distributed
 181 around the parent points, with a mean of zero and standard deviation of σ . The theoretical
 182 K -function for a PCP is as follows.

$$183 \quad K(r; \rho, \sigma) = \pi r^2 + \frac{1 - e^{(-r^2/4\sigma^2)}}{\rho}, \quad (2)$$

184 **Estimation of the K -function for replicated data and between-group comparisons with**
 185 **a two-factorial design.**

186 A detailed description of the method for the one-way design proposed by Diggle et al.
 187 (1991) and modified by Diggle (2003) is presented in Appendix 1 in the Supplementary
 188 Material. If we have an experimental or observational design with two crossed factors, i.e.,
 189 A with levels $i = 1, \dots, a$, and B with levels $j = 1, \dots, b$, then it is straightforward to extend
 190 the approach proposed by Diggle et al. (1991). Thus, the structure of the model used to
 191 describe the data is:

$$192 \quad K_{ijk}(r) = K_0(r) + A_i + B_j + A_i B_j + e_{ijk}(r), \quad (3)$$

193 where $K_{ijk}(r)$ is the K -function for the k th replicate in the ij th cell of the observational or
 194 experimental design; A_i , B_j , and $A_i B_j$ are the effects of the corresponding levels of factors A,
 195 B, and their interaction, respectively; $K_0(r)$ is the overall mean K -function (defined below),
 196 and $e_{ijk}(r)$ is the residual error associated with the function $K_{ijk}(r)$.

197 In the case of a two-factorial design, it is necessary to test for the existence of an interaction
 198 between the two factors because the main factors cannot be interpreted if one exists. A
 199 statistic analogous to the sum of squares for the interaction term in a two-way ANOVA is:

$$200 \quad BTSS = \sum_{i=1}^a \sum_{j=1}^b n_{ij} \int_0^{r_0} w(r) \{ \widehat{K}_{ij}(r) - \widehat{K}_i(r) - \widehat{K}_j(r) + \widehat{K}_0(r) \}^2 dr, \quad (4)$$

201 where n_{ij} is the total number of points (summed up among the k replicates) in the ij th cell of
 202 the experimental design (i.e., the total number of points in the plots within the combined
 203 levels i and j), r_0 is the largest scale (i.e., the maximum r) of interest in terms of spatial
 204 differences, $w(r)$ is a function for normalizing large scale variations in the differences
 205 between K -functions (e.g., $w(r) = r^{-2}$), $\widehat{K}_0(r)$ is the overall weighted average K -function,
 206 and $\widehat{K}_{ij}(r)$, $\widehat{K}_i(r)$, and $\widehat{K}_j(r)$ are the weighted average K -functions estimated for different
 207 levels and combinations of levels for the factors A and B. For a particular level or
 208 combination of levels l , the average K -functions are estimated as

$$209 \quad \widehat{K}_l(r) = \sum_{x=1}^{m_l} n_x \widehat{K}_x(r) / \sum_{x=1}^{m_l} n_x, \quad (5)$$

210 where m_l is the number of replicates for that particular level or combination of levels, and
 211 n_x and $\widehat{K}_x(r)$ are the number of points and the K -function for each replicate x , respectively.

212 Following the approach described by Diggle et al. (1991), we use sampling with
 213 replacement to estimate the sampling distribution of the between treatments sum of squares
 214 ($BTSS$). First, we compute the residual function for the k th replicate within the combination
 215 of the i th and j th groups as follows.

$$216 \quad R_{ijk}(r) = n_{ijk}^{0.5} [\widehat{K}_{ijk}(r) - \widehat{K}_i(r) - \widehat{K}_j(r) + \widehat{K}_0(r)]. \quad (6)$$

217 Including (and subtracting) $\widehat{K}_i(r)$ and $\widehat{K}_j(r)$ allows the individual effects of factors A and B
218 to be removed, which guarantees that the residual functions are exchangeable under the null
219 and alternative hypotheses (Anderson and Ter Braak 2003).

220 According to the single-factor analysis described by Diggle et al. (1991), if we sample with
221 replacement from the set of residual functions $\widehat{R}_{ijk}(r)$, then we obtain resamples
222 $R_{ijk}^*(r): k = 1, \dots, m_{ij}; i = 1, \dots, a; j = 1, \dots, b$, which we can use to compute a set of
223 resampled K -functions under the null hypothesis of no interaction as follows.

$$224 \quad \widehat{K}_{ijk}^* = \widehat{K}_i(r) + \widehat{K}_j(r) - \widehat{K}_0 + n_{ijk}^{-0.5} R_{ijk}^*(r). \quad (7)$$

225 Again, each resample is a complete set of K -functions (i.e., as many functions as there are
226 replicates in the study), which is used to compute a resampled $BTSS$ value.

227 Inference of the test result is obtained by comparing the observed $BTSS$ value with the
228 distribution of s resampled $BTSS$ values. In the case where the null hypothesis of no
229 interaction is not rejected, we can proceed to test the effects of each of the individual
230 factors, possibly by using the method of Diggle et al. (1991) for the one-factor case.

231 **Analysis of validity and power of the test for interaction effects**

232 To analyze the validity and power of the test proposed for detecting interactions, we
233 followed the procedure described by Diggle et al. (1991). We tested the validity of the test
234 in the context of our study (i.e., its ability to yield an acceptable probability of making a
235 type I error) by employing a bootstrap procedure to generate 1000 sets of 16 replicated
236 patterns (i.e., the same number of replicates used in our study), which were simulated to
237 conform with the null hypothesis (i.e., the absence of interaction). If the test is valid, we

238 expect that the probability of rejecting the null hypothesis would be near to its nominal (α)
239 value.

240 We simulated replicates with similar abundances and spatial patterns to those observed.
241 Most of them exhibited clear aggregated patterns, so we first fitted a PCP (Diggle 2003) to
242 each of the 16 observed replicates, which allowed us to select the parameters for our
243 simulations. In order to simulate the null hypothesis of no interaction, we simulated two
244 subsets where each had eight replicates, one of which was highly aggregated (mean
245 intensity of clusters $\rho = 0.0178$, i.e., 16.1 clusters per plot) whereas the other was less
246 aggregated (mean $\rho = 0.0593$, i.e., 53.4 clusters per plot). In both cases, the dispersion was
247 set to $\sigma = 5$ m. These parameters were selected arbitrarily from among the range of
248 parameters fitted to the original patterns. The “highly aggregated” and “less aggregated”
249 patterns were assigned to the levels “flat” and “steep” for the factor slope, respectively,
250 whereas the levels “low” and “high” for factor altitude were assigned randomly to each
251 replicate. The numbers of points simulated for each replicate were similar to those recorded
252 in the observed replicates.

253 In order to evaluate the power of the test and its dependence on the differences in clustering
254 between replicates, we implemented 1000 more simulations (16 replicates each) for each of
255 a series of different scenarios of the alternative hypothesis (presence of interaction). In
256 these simulations, we assigned a fixed, less aggregated structure (PCP with $\rho = 0.39$, i.e.,
257 around 350 clusters per plot) to the plots using the combinations of “low altitude–steep
258 slope” and “high altitude–flat slope”, whereas for all of the other groups (plots with the
259 combinations of “low altitude–flat slope” and “high altitude–steep slope”), we simulated

260 more aggregated PCP processes ($\rho = 0.350$ to $\rho = 0.001$, i.e., from 315 to only one cluster
261 per plot).

262 **Statistical analyses**

263 Using our procedure, we tested for the existence of an interaction between the effects of
264 altitude and slope on the spatial pattern of *C. wagneri*. We computed $K(r)$ functions from r
265 = 0 to 8 m at 0.05 m intervals and using isotropic edge correction. To compute the *BTSS*,
266 we set $w(r) = r^{-2}$, according to Diggle (2003). The significance of the computed statistic
267 was evaluated with 1000 bootstrap resamples.

268 To compare the performance of our approach with an alternative method, we also
269 performed rank-based ANOVA (Hetmansperger and McKean 2011) to analyze the
270 variation among the observational groups for the parameter σ in the PCPs fitted to each
271 actual *C. wagneri* pattern. This parameter is usually employed as a measure of the degree of
272 aggregation of spatial patterns and it has been employed to assess differences among
273 patterns generated by different processes (e.g., Seidler and Plotkin 2006, Jara-Guerrero et
274 al. 2015).

275 All of the calculations were conducted in R (R Core Team 2013) using the packages “Rfit”
276 (Kloke and McKean 2012), “spatstat” (Baddeley and Turner 2005), and “ecspa” (De la
277 Cruz 2008). The functions employed to compute and test the *BTSS* statistic in both the one-
278 and two-way designs are included in the R package “replicatedpp2w.”

279

280 **Results**

281 In all of the plots, the observed K -functions had patterns that were compatible with PCPs
282 (Table 1, Fig. 3), whereas some plots also exhibited small-scale inhibition (for $r < 1$ m)
283 (Fig. 3). In general, the plots of flat slopes at low altitude and the plots of steep slopes at
284 high altitude exhibited less clustering than the rest, although the group of flat slopes at a
285 low altitude was the most aggregated at fine scales ($r < 1$ m; Fig. 3 and Fig. 4).

286 The analysis confirmed the existence of a significant interaction effect between slope and
287 altitude on the spatial pattern of *Croton* ($p = 0.009$; Fig. 4; Table 2).

288 In general, our validity analysis (Table S1) showed that the test's performance was quite
289 close to the nominal value. Given the small p value obtained in our study (0.009), we are
290 confident that the null hypothesis of no interaction can be rejected, at least at the $\alpha = 0.05$
291 level. In addition, and quite logically, the power of the test increased as the differences in
292 the numbers of clusters between combinations of factor levels increased (Table S2).

293 By contrast, the rank-based ANOVA analysis could not confirm the existence of a
294 difference in the fitted σ values among the altitude and slope groups, or of an interaction
295 (Table 3).

296 **Discussion**

297 Our method for analyzing replicated patterns aims to detect interactions between
298 experimental or observational factors. In our case study, the spatial pattern of all the
299 populations was aggregated. If we had employed the usual approach of using just one plot
300 or simply obtaining a weighted average of the replicated plots to analyze the spatial pattern
301 of *Croton wagneri*, we could only have concluded that the shrub exhibited aggregation,

302 which is unsurprising given that it is a dispersal-limited species (Jara-Guerrero et al. 2011).
303 By using the approach described by Diggle et al. (1991) to analyze the individual effects of
304 slope or altitude, we could have concluded that altitude was irrelevant to the spatial
305 organization of *C. wagneri*. However, using our new non-parametric two-way approach, we
306 were able to determine that the spatial pattern of *C. wagneri* appeared to be driven by the
307 interaction between altitude and slope (Fig. 5). This result could not have been obtained
308 using the more traditional approach (e.g., Seidler and Plotkin 2006) based on comparing the
309 parameters of individual fitted PCPs (Table 3). Alternatively, if spatially explicit
310 environmental variables are available, we can use them for parametric estimation of the
311 intensity functions in each plot (Law et al. 2009, Wiegand and Moloney 2014). The
312 regression parameters of the intensity functions would then show how the plant density
313 depends on the environment, while fitting inhomogeneous PCPs (Waagepetersen 2007)
314 would demonstrate how the residual clustering depends on the environment.

315 We hypothesized that differences in aridity would generate differences in aggregation
316 between the low- and high-altitude *Croton* populations growing on flat ground, and that
317 topography would exacerbate the effect of aridity in populations growing on steep slopes,
318 thereby promoting the greatest aggregation, irrespective of altitude. We expected that this
319 would be detected as a significant interaction effect in our two-way analysis. In fact, a
320 significant interaction was detected, but it was probably caused by a different mechanism.
321 First, the aggregation on steep slopes was not equally uniform, but instead it differed
322 between low and high altitudes, where the plots on steep slopes at a high altitude exhibited
323 the lowest aggregation on average. Second, in contrast to our initial hypothesis, the highest
324 average aggregation occurred in the populations growing on flat ground at high altitude.

325 This is surprising because this combination does not seem to be the most stressful. Nurse
326 effects and thus more aggregated patterns are expected to be more important in the sites
327 with the most severe environmental conditions (e.g., drier areas at low altitude; Flores and
328 Jurado 2003, Maestre et al. 2009), but other mechanisms could explain the differences in
329 the aggregation of *C. wagneri* among sites. First, *C. wagneri* is a barochorous species so it
330 is intrinsically dispersal-limited (Jara-Guerrero et al. 2011), which could affect the expected
331 spatial structures due to scale-dependent feedback between plants and soil water
332 availability (Pueyo et al. 2008). Second, *Croton* seeds have the potential for secondary
333 dispersal by ants (Jara-Guerrero et al. 2011), which could differ with altitude (Smith et al.
334 1989) and interfere with the formation of the spatial structure of *C. wagneri* via other
335 mechanisms (Kalisz et al. 1999, Zhou et al. 2007).

336 We suspect that the “unexpected” results obtained for the populations growing on flat
337 ground at low and high altitudes were a consequence of a shift in the vegetation structure in
338 response to the decrease in aridity with altitude. Deblawe et al. (2011) showed that a
339 decrease in aridity caused a transition from isolated “spots” to larger connected masses
340 (“labyrinths”) of standing biomass. In fact, the average σ parameter among the fitted PCPs
341 was highest for the populations on flat ground at high altitude ($\sigma = 7.92$ m, corresponding
342 to an average cluster size of 22.40 m). This was linked to the prevalence of heterogeneous
343 patterns among these plots because the existence of large patches leads to the appearance of
344 virtual aggregation (Wiegand and Moloney 2014). Previously, this has been treated as a
345 nuisance (Schiffers et al. 2008), but the existence of virtual aggregation in our plots
346 reflected the large scale ecological processes that actually control the spatial structure of *C.*
347 *wagneri*. By contrast, the fitted values for σ were smallest in the populations on flat ground

348 at low altitude (average $\sigma = 1.96$ m, corresponding to a cluster size of 5.54 m), which could
349 help to explain why the average K -function for this group was the highest at small scales
350 (Fig. 4). In summary, there was a transition from small abundant spots at low altitude (i.e.,
351 more severe conditions) to a small number of large patches at high altitude. Thus,
352 irrespective of (or in addition to) nurse effects and limited dispersal, our results suggest that
353 the spatial organization of *C. wagneri* is driven mainly by eco-hydrological feedback
354 processes (Pueyo et al. 2008).

355 The effect of slope varied greatly among altitudes. In contrast to our initial hypothesis, the
356 lowest spatial aggregation appeared on the steep slope plots at high altitude. The average
357 size of the patches in these plots did not differ greatly from those in the high altitude plots
358 on flat ground ($\sigma = 7.15$ m), but they exhibited the largest spatial inhibition at fine scales
359 (Supplementary information; Figure S2). We used the K -function to measure spatial
360 aggregation, which has “memory” (Wiegand and Moloney 2014), so the low densities at
361 small scales influenced (i.e., decreased) the value of the function at larger scales, and thus
362 the final results at these scales were apparently “less aggregated.” In fact, if we had
363 employed the approach of Wiegand et al. (2007, 2009) to remove the confounding effects
364 of small scale inhibition on the K -function and refitted the Poisson cluster models, we
365 would have obtained results compatible with greater aggregation (e.g., average refitted $\sigma =$
366 2.56 m). Regardless of the method employed, the spatial inhibition reached up to 0.8 m,
367 which excludes the existence of nurse effects at this location.

368 In addition, the increased spatial aggregation with respect to flat ground populations at low
369 altitude was caused by an increase in the average size of the patches ($\sigma = 4.62$ m; average
370 size = 13.01 m) and a parallel decrease in their number (average number of clusters per plot

371 = 18.2). According to the same reasoning employed previously, this suggests that the
372 hydrological environment was better on the slopes than that on the flat ground, which
373 appears odd. An alternative or complementary hypothesis may be related to the fact that
374 *Croton* was at its uppermost local limit, which suggests that the climate conditions were far
375 from its optimum at these sites. Therefore, the physiological performance of *Croton* would
376 have been limited under these milder conditions and thus the species may have been
377 severely stressed. This paradoxical situation where the worst performance occurred on flat
378 ground is compatible with the patterns found in the steep, high altitude scenarios simply
379 because more xeric conditions are physiologically favorable for this species.

380 In conclusion, our new method combined with replicated point patterns obtained from an
381 appropriate sampling or experimental design can yield insights that are difficult to obtain
382 using other spatial techniques. Our method is easy to apply and the results can be
383 interpreted in a straightforward manner in ecological terms. In addition, the reliability and
384 power of our method can be assessed easily in any specific context. This method could be
385 extended to a more general model-based approach, which could include a number of factors
386 and covariates (i.e., continuous variables) obtained from observational or experimental
387 studies. We consider that the use of replicated spatial point pattern analyses by ecologists
388 should be encouraged in the future.

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515 genetic structure of *Globba lancangensis* (Zingiberaceae). - J. Hered. 98(4): 317-324.
- 516

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518 **Table 1.** Summary of the plot attributes. Altitude: meters above sea level. N: number of points (shrubs) per
 519 plot. Canopy: mean canopy area \pm 1 standard error, estimated by the area of an ellipse from the canopy
 520 diameters. Parameters of the Poisson cluster process fixed to each plot. n_c : number of clusters ($= \rho \times 300 \text{ m} \times$
 521 300 m), μ : mean number of points per cluster, σ : dispersion parameter.

Plot	Altitude (m)	Slope	N	Canopy (m ²)	n_c	μ	σ (m)
1	1400	flat	859	0.2056 \pm 0.0120	36.2	23.7	2.45
2	1400	flat	239	0.1379 \pm 0.0137	79.8	3.0	1.14
3	1400	steep	285	0.2295 \pm 0.0194	1.8	162.0	8.78
4	1400	steep	395	0.2219 \pm 0.0207	20.0	19.8	2.93
5	1500	flat	815	0.1562 \pm 0.0069	38.1	21.4	3.00
6	1500	flat	724	0.0960 \pm 0.0067	165.0	4.4	1.24
7	1500	steep	296	0.2972 \pm 0.0260	33.2	9.0	2.86
8	1500	steep	665	0.1257 \pm 0.0079	18.3	36.4	3.90
9	1750	flat	650	0.1303 \pm 0.0111	30.5	21.3	2.15
10	1750	flat	679	0.3328 \pm 0.0190	19.2	35.4	3.30
11	1750	steep	1959	0.055 \pm 0.0022	81.0	24.2	2.05
12	1750	steep	541	0.313 \pm 0.0246	59.4	9.1	2.79
13	1900	flat	561	0.3397 \pm 0.0319	9.6	58.4	4.19
14	1900	flat	732	0.2865 \pm 0.0174	1.4	536.6	22.04
15	1900	steep	879	0.0513 \pm 0.0045	29.1	30.2	4.94
16	1900	steep	571	0.2430 \pm 0.0187	1.7	342.9	18.82

522

523

524 **Table 2.** Results of the non-parametric analysis of the replicated *Croton wagneri* point patterns. *BTSS*: sum of
525 squared differences. *p*-value estimated after 1000 samples with replacement (bootstrap) of the residual
526 functions. To calculate the *BTSS*, we used $K(r)$ functions estimated from $r = 0.05$ to $r = 8$ m, at intervals of
527 0.05 m.

Factor	<i>BTSS</i>	<i>p</i> -value
Slope	1373518.4	0.039
Altitude	259998.3	0.408
Slope–Altitude	2086014.1	0.009

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533 **Table 3.** Rank-based ANOVA results for the variation among groups of the σ parameter in the Poisson cluster
534 process fitted to each point pattern. Df: degrees of freedom.

	Df	<i>F</i> value	<i>p</i> -value
Altitude	1	0.625	0.444
Slope	1	0.534	0.479
Altitude–Slope	1	0.663	0.431
Residuals	12		

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539

540 **Figure 1** (A) Shrubland dominated by *Croton wagneri*. (B) Study site location.

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551

552 **Figure 2.** Representative point patterns of each combination of slope and altitude. Numbers above the panels
 553 correspond to the plot numbers in Table 1, i.e., 6: low altitude, flat slope; 7: low altitude, steep slope; 14: high
 554 altitude, flat slope; 15: high altitude, steep slope.

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556

557 **Figure 3** K -functions for the *Croton wagneri* point patterns under different altitude (number in meters) and
 558 slope conditions. We show the $L(r)$ function for representation and interpretation purposes, where $L(r) =$
 559 $\sqrt{K(r)/\pi} - r$ is a standardized version of $K(r)$ (Besag 1977). For a random pattern, the function $L(r)$ has an
 560 expected value of 0 at all distances r (Dixon 2001). The continuous black lines represent the empirical values
 561 of $L(r) - r$ and the dashed red lines represent the $L(r) - r$ function of a Poisson cluster process fitted to each
 562 *Croton wagneri* pattern.

564

565 **Figure 4** Averaged $K(r)$ functions for each combination of factor levels (transformed as $L(r) = \sqrt{K(r)}/\pi -$
 566 r) to facilitate interpretation). CSR: expected value for a plot with complete spatial randomness. Global:
 567 overall average $K(r)$ function.

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569

570 **Figure 5** Differences in spatial aggregation between plots. Red boxes: plots on flat slopes; white boxes: plots
 571 on steep slopes. “Spatial aggregation” was measured for each plot as the sum of values of the $L(r)$ function
 572 [$L(r) = \sqrt{K(r)/\pi} - r$]. For all plots, $K(r)$ was computed for $r = 0$ to $r = 8$ with 0.05 m intervals. The
 573 expected value of the empirical L -function for a completely random process is $L(r) = 0$, whereas positive
 574 values indicate aggregation.

575